

Supplementary Tables for “Explainable AI (XAI) in decision support for mitigating carbon emissions in agriculture: A Systematic Review”

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General Note: This document provides the supplementary material for the paper titled "Explainable AI (XAI) in decision support for mitigating carbon emissions in agriculture: A Systematic Review," containing all the necessary tables for the full understanding of the systematic review method and results. This material includes the detailed inclusion and exclusion criteria, the complete list of titles and identifiers of the selected primary studies, as well as all result analysis tables, covering the frequencies of each identified category and their respective detailed descriptions. Due to the space limitations of the short paper format, this extended document is provided to ensure methodological transparency and to offer a granular view of the synthesized data.

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Table 1: Inclusion Criteria.

ID	Description	Justification
IC01	Studies in the form of articles or conference papers.	Avoid gray literature.
IC02	Studies published in English.	Language read by the author and international standard
IC03	Studies published from 2023 onwards.	During the search string test, only studies relevant to the topic from that date onwards were found.
IC04	Studies necessarily involved in the field of Computing.	Author's research area.
IC05	Studies applied to the agricultural context.	Specific context of the research.
IC06	Studies with some Explainable AI (XAI) techniques applied.	The importance of explainability for the auditability, reliability, and transparency of studies in the AI field.

Table 2: Exclusion Criteria.

ID	Description	Justification
EC01	Studies without full access for the institution of affiliation or open access.	Resources available to the author.
EC02	Duplicate studies.	Avoid duplicate results.
EC03	Studies outside the research topic (without contributing to answering the research question).	Avoid confusion in the results and unproductive review.
EC04	Studies consisting solely of reviews or abstracts.	Need for primary data.
EC05	Studies published before 2023.	Not obtained in the selection
EC06	Studies with ML-based results based solely on metrics unrelated to interpretability or explainability.	Avoid studies with "black box" focus, contrary to the intent of the research focused on explainability.
EC07	Studies that do not mention the area of Explainable AI (XAI).	Avoid studies that are unaware of or do not consider the best practices developed by the XAI area.

Table 3: PICOC Elements.

Element	Content (search terms)
Population /Problem	ML models linked to carbon emissions
Intervention	Explainable AI (XAI) techniques
Comparison	Black-box models
Outcome	Explainable strategies for producers and public policymakers.
Context	Agricultural

Table 4: Specific research questions.

ID	Question
RQ1	Which XAI technical tools have been applied in agriculture and carbon emissions?
RQ2	How do the identified XAI methods contribute to explainability in the systems where they have been employed?
RQ3	In which specific areas of carbon mitigation have XAI techniques been applied?
RQ4	What types of decisions by rural producers and public policymakers have been aided or enabled by the impact of XAI use?

Table 5: Selected studies.

ID	Title	Year	Reference
E01	Digital mapping of peat thickness and extent in Finland using remote sensing and machine learning	2025	(Pohjankukka et al., 2025)
E02	Enhancing soil organic carbon prediction by unraveling the role of crop residue coverage using interpretable machine learning	2025	(Dong et al., 2025)
E03	Game analysis of future rice yield changes in China based on explainable machine-learning and planting date optimization	2024	(Zhang et al., 2024)
E04	High-performance prediction of soil organic carbon using automatic hyperparameter optimization method in the Yellow River Delta of China	2025	(Song et al., 2025)
E05	Identification of factors influencing net primary productivity of terrestrial ecosystems based on interpretable machine learning - evidence from the county-level administrative districts in China	2023	(Yi & Wu, 2023)
E06	Leveraging explainable AI to predict soil respiration sensitivity and its drivers for climate change mitigation	2025	(Novielli et al., 2025)
E07	Machine learning-driven analysis of greenhouse gas emissions from rice production in major Chinese provinces: Identifying key factors and developing reduction strategies	2025	(Huan & Liu, 2025)

E08	Modeling Global Warming from Agricultural CO2 Emissions: From Worldwide Patterns to the Case of Iran	2025	(Pourdarbani et al., 2025)
E09	Monitoring of greenhouse gas emission drivers in Atlantic Canadian Potato production: A robust explainable intelligent glass-box	2024	(Jamei et al., 2024)
E10	Predictive modelling employing machine learning, convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and smartphone RGB images for non-destructive biomass estimation of pearl millet (<i>Pennisetum glaucum</i>)	2025	(Dhawi et al., 2025)
E11	Understanding the agriculture sectors of greenhouse gas emissions prediction in the global scenario: Insights from explainable artificial intelligence (XAI)	2025	(Sireesha & Sheik, 2025)
E12	Utilizing Machine Learning to Understand and Predict Methane Emissions in Cattle Farming with Farm-Scale Environmental and Biological Variables	2024	(Partridge et al., 2024)

Table 6: Tools identified in the selected studies.

Name	Type	A.F. ⁶	R.F. ⁷	Studies
Feature Engineering and Feature Selection				
Correlation-based Feature Pruning	Metric-Centric Process	3	25,0%	E01, E02, E08
Genetic Algorithm	Feature Selection Algorithm	1	8,3%	E01
Boruta	Feature Selection Algorithm	1	8,3%	E09
Best Subset Lasso Regression (BSLR)	Feature Selection Algorithm	1	8,3%	E09
WASPAS	Feature Selection Algorithm	1	8,3%	E09
t-SNE	Dimensionality Reduction Algorithm	1	8,3%	E06
Insight Generation				
SHAP	Approach as Coding Library	12	100,0%	All
LIME	Approach as Coding Library	1	8,3%	E11
SHAP Dependence Plots	Internal SHAP Usage	2	16,7%	E02, E05
SHAP Interaction Plots	Internal SHAP Usage	1	8,3%	E05
TreeSHAP	Model-Specific SHAP	1	8,3%	E08
KernelSHAP	Model-Specific SHAP	1	8,3%	E08
Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE) plots	Plots	1	8,3%	E11
Partial Dependence Plots (PDP's)	Plots	1	8,3%	E11
Impurity-Based Feature Importance	Metric-Centric Process	1	8,3%	E08

⁶ Absolute frequency.

⁷ Relative frequency.

Permutation Feature Importance (PFI)	Permutation Technique	1	8,3%	E01
Variogram Decomposition	Statistical Analysis Method	1	8,3%	E04
Hierarchical partitioning (HP)	Statistical Analysis Method	1	8,3%	E04
Uncertainty Analysis				
Random Forest Agreement	Internal ML Model Process	1	8,3%	E01
Bootstrapping	Statistical Technique	1	8,3%	E02
ML Models				
Random Forest	Ensemble Learning	7	58,3%	E01, E02, E03, E07, E08, E10, E12
XGBoost	Ensemble Learning	5	41,7%	E04, E05, E07, E08, E10
GradientBoosting / GBDT / GRANDE	Ensemble Learning	5	41,7%	E04, E08, E09, E10, E12
LightGBM	Ensemble Learning	3	25,0%	E07, E08, E09
ExtraTree Classifier	Ensemble Learning	1	8,3%	E06
AdaBoost	Ensemble Learning	1	8,3%	E12
Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)	Deep Learning	3	25,0%	E04, E10, E11
Multilayer Perceptron (MLP)	Deep Learning	3	25,0%	E08, E11, E12
Deep Forest	Deep Learning	1	8,3%	E04
Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN)	Deep Learning	1	8,3%	E11
KMeans Clustering	Clustering	2	16,7%	E05, E06
Agglomerative Clustering	Clustering	1	8,3%	E06
Birch Clustering	Clustering	1	8,3%	E06
Partial Least Squares (PLS)	Linear Regression	1	8,3%	E03
ElasticNET	Linear Regression Extension	1	8,3%	E12
Generalized Linear Model (GLM)	Linear Regression Extension	1	8,3%	E03
Generalized Additive Model (GAM)	Linear Regression Extension	1	8,3%	E03
SVM/SVR's	Supervised Learning	1	8,3%	E10
Network on Network (NON)	Deep Architecture	1	8,3%	E08
Gated Recurrent Units (GRU's)	Deep Architecture	1	8,3%	E11
Hyperparameter Optimization				
Grey Wolf Optimization (GWO)	Nature-Inspired Algorithm	2	16,7%	E04, E07
Hunter-Prey Optimization (HPO)	Nature-Inspired Algorithm	1	8,3%	E04
Bayesian Optimization	Probabilistic Model	2	16,7%	E04, E07

Runge-Kutta	Numerical Algorithm	1	8,3%	E09
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Table 7: Explainability Analysis Categories for RQ2.

Category name	Explanation / Description	Origin
Phenomenological dependency analysis with feature importance	Evaluates the weight of specific variables in the prediction of environmental phenomena, relating the measured importance to the modeled behavior.	Widely referenced in XAI
Capturing non-linear relationships	Revealing complex patterns and response curves where input variation does not follow a linear relationship with the output.	Widely referenced in XAI
Local-global comparison	Contrasting feature behavior for local prediction versus the general trend of the entire dataset (global). Helps explain regional and specific phenomena.	Widely referenced in XAI
Capturing interaction and synergistic relationships	Revealing how the joint interaction of two or more features changes the prediction impact.	Widely referenced in XAI
Detecting multicollinearity problems	Identification of redundant or correlated features that confound the model and skew the measured importance.	Widely referenced in XAI
Identifying domain thresholds	Identification of critical points and specific values in variables that significantly alter prediction behavior.	Widely referenced in XAI
Prediction error diagnosis	Detailed investigation of errors to explain the reasons for model failures.	Widely referenced in XAI
Explainable feature engineering	Interpretability-led feature engineering and transformation to ensure model inputs maintain domain-specific meaning and foster transparent relationships.	Proposed by the author for this study
Clustering of explanations	Employing XAI data to cluster instances based on their similar functional behavior within the model.	Proposed by the author for this study
Hyperparameter explanations	Assessment of how hyperparameter configurations shape the resulting model explanations.	Proposed by the author for this study
Spatial uncertainty mapping of models	Mapping the geographic reliability and margins of error to detect zones of increased uncertainty in georeferenced environments.	Proposed by the author for this study
Hidden heterogeneity identification in groups	Identification of variations within a group previously defined by domain knowledge. Capturing data that react differently than expected for that group.	Proposed by the author for this study
Discovering counter-intuitive relationships	Identification of model behaviors that challenge prior domain knowledge (e.g., temperature increases promoting carbon accumulation), generating new insights.	Proposed by the author for this study

Table 8: Explainability Analysis Categories identified in the selected studies.

Category name	A.F.	R.F.	Studies
Phenomenological dependency analysis with feature importance	12	100,0%	All
Capturing non-linear relationships	5	41,7%	E02, E04, E05, E07, E11
Local-global comparison	4	33,3%	E05, E08, E09, E11
Capturing interaction and synergistic relationships	3	25,0%	E04, E05, E11

Discovering counter-intuitive relationships	3	25,0%	E03, E04, E05
Explainable feature engineering	2	16,7%	E09, E10
Spatial uncertainty mapping of models	2	16,7%	E01, E02
Identifying domain thresholds	2	16,7%	E02, E07
Clustering of explanations	2	16,7%	E05, E06
Hyperparameter explanations	2	16,7%	E04, E05
Hidden heterogeneity identification in groups	2	16,7%	E06, E11
Prediction error diagnosis	1	8,3%	E08
Detecting multicollinearity problems	1	8,3%	E12

Table 9: Application domains and activities identified.

Activity	A.F.	R.F.	Studies
Greenhouse gas (GHG) emission forecasting	5	41,7%	E07, E08, E09, E11, E12
Digital soil mapping (DSM)	3	25,0%	E01, E02, E04
Soil Organic Carbon (SOC) prediction	2	16,7%	E02, E04
Conservation of carbon sinks	2	16,7%	E01, E05
Peat thickness and extent mapping	1	8,3%	E01
Crop yield forecasting	1	8,3%	E03
Soil respiration sensitivity forecasting	1	8,3%	E06
Above-Ground Biomass (AGB) estimation	1	8,3%	E10
Net Primary Productivity (NPP) forecasting	1	8,3%	E05
Livestock enteric emission forecasting	1	8,3%	E12

Table 10: Decision Support Categories for RQ4.

Category name	Explanation / Description	Target audience	Studies
Regional or national land-use planning	Definition of zoning and identification of priority areas for conservation, restoration, or agriculture based on the carbon potential explained by the model.	Public policymakers	E01, E02, E04, E05
Assessing the suitability of model data for specific farm areas	Assessment of local/regional prediction confidence, allowing the user to validate whether the model correctly applies to the territory or specific conditions of their property.	Rural producers	E01, E02, E05, E06, E07
Agroclimatic management and phenological calendar	Alignment of agricultural management decisions with climatic and microclimatic conditions. This involves adjusting the planting calendar and phenology, as well as other optimizations in response to temperature, humidity, etc.	Both	E03, E07, E09

Low-cost real-time monitoring	Instant estimates in the field via smartphones, democratizing access to precision metrics.	Rural producers ⁸	E10
Crop residue management	Decision on the optimal amount of biomass to be maintained in the soil to optimize soil organic carbon (SOC) sequestration based on identified thresholds.	Rural producers	E02
Fertilizer management	Optimization of chemical input or nitrogen compound dosages guided by the identification of factors with the greatest impact on GHG emissions in trade-off with productivity.	Rural producers	E07
Drainage strategies	Strategic management of peatlands or control of flooded areas.	Both	E01, E07
Methane emission	Mapping of macro-actors and critical sectors in methane emissions and measurement of the impact of methane on overall emissions.	Public policymakers	E11, E12
Ruminant dietary strategies	Modification of animal nutrition based on the importance of dietary variables that directly affect enteric fermentation and associated emissions.	Rural producers	E12

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⁸ Of potentially greater importance to environmental engineers as well.

- T. Partridge, B. Li, B. Alhnaity, & Q. Meng. (2024). Utilizing Machine Learning to Understand and Predict Methane Emissions in Cattle Farming with Farm-Scale Environmental and Biological Variables. *2024 International Conference on Computer and Applications (ICCA)*, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCA62237.2024.10927962>
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